

3rd International Study Day of

NaKaN Learned Society

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"BACK TO AFRICA"

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Situated at the heart of contemporary geopolitical issues, Africa must now face up to the ecological emergency, the energy transition, the demographic challenge and changing economic models (Leyronas, Coriat and Nubukpo, 2023). By taking stock of its ancestral history and millennia of experience, spanning pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial periods (Ki-Zerbo, 1972), we can now propose a different way of thinking about the world and its tensions from its margins. This observation leads us to consider the relationship between Africa and its diasporas from a centrifugal perspective, in addition to the traditionally centripetal one. The latter, centred on Africa, emphasises Africa's contribution to humanity. It is therefore essential to emphasise the importance of Afrodiasporic communities returning to their roots, and the material, immaterial, territorial and extra-territorial transfers that this entails. The poet Léopold Sédar Senghor already foresaw this importance. In fact, he made Africa, where knowledge is to be found, the source of his art, and advocated referring to it "as manatees go to drink from the source of the Simal" (Senghor, 2017).

How can the return of these communities from Africa take place in the era of transmodernity and postcoloniality? What are the triggers and the cultural, social, political and economic modalities of this process? What are the symbolic, theoretical and epistemological stakes of such an approach in a world where diasporic soft power is intensifying?

If the relationship with Africa can be fixed by neo-colonial representations, whether exogenous or endogenous to the continent, relayed as much by the visions of African researchers as by those of European analysts, this highlights the dichotomy employed by Obenga, evoking Afrocentricity versus Eurocentric Africanism (Obenga, 2001). This underlines the rise of African historical and cultural awareness, and legitimises the critical return to a reflection on the relationship with origins, thus placing contemporary African worlds at the heart of the dynamics of identity reconstruction.

From an individual perspective, this can be extended to Afro-descendants facing physical and symbolic violence, as well as the destruction of cultural and natural ecosystems caused by global capitalism (Mbembe, 2020). From an intersubjective and strategic point of view, it is essential to situate the African continent and the immense diversity of its

contributions to the world's tangible and intangible heritage. This undeniable reality can be seen in the relationship between ancient and traditional art and contemporary art, as well as in the existence of an African aesthetic and artistic landscape (Mbaye Diop, 2011). It is crucial to remember the immense debt we owe to it. In addition to the duty of presence, which can be concretised through the economy of restitution of truths and works of art (Sarr and Savoy, 2018), diasporic citizenship must be conceived in terms of physical return or collaboration. This could foster the emergence of new disciplinary or transdisciplinary paradigms, full of meaning and future.

It is undeniable that the symbolic and spiritual dimension runs through the entire cultural ecosystem of Afrodiasporas, regardless of where they settle (forced or voluntary), and continues to structure literary (Malela, 2022), artistic (Lefrançois, 2022), mythological (M'baye, 2011), political (Appiah, 1993) and musical consciousness. The participatory and community-based structures of African music feed the creative imagination of composers and performers the world over, because the ramifications of music beyond the continent are like musical responses to social, identity and cultural changes in the contemporary world (Agawu, 2020). From a pragmatic and praxemic point of view, the question of reattaching the languages of the deported African community groups, as well as the repositioning of all the Creole languages of the Americas, born of contact between African languages (Bantu, Niger-Congo and Shamitic) and European languages, in a continuum of belonging, is a social fact, but remains to be constructed and translated into concrete practices and imaginations.

Historically, pan-Africanism has spawned courageous initiatives to encourage a return to the Mother Earth of origins, under the aegis of thinkers such as Edward Dermot Blyden, Marcus Garvey, and others who have contributed to the creation of new spaces for transnational encounters and relations. The creation of Afrodiasporic states such as Sierra Leone and Liberia (A. N. Bell, 2018) bears witness to this, but has also highlighted the thorny issue of integrating returnees into a religiously and culturally different social fabric (C. Phillips, 1995). This underlines the fact that, beyond the purely ontological, identity-related or aesthetic dimension, the inscription and reconnection of the Afrodescendant diasporic subject in the ancestral lineage remains a huge task that we must grasp and question.

Expressing the issue of return in dynamic, existential or artistic terms provides an opportunity to link up with diverse and fruitful forms of thought, but does not prevent us from assessing the limits and obstacles to making return a reality, particularly in economic and logistical terms. The aim of our third study day is precisely to address all these issues from a projective and praxemic perspective, but also to transcend common sense discourses on Africa and its diasporas, in order to be better rooted in an objectified and modelisable approach to the realities linked to the question of the return of diasporic subjects today.

Some possible avenues to explore:

- African diasporic perspectives in the era of transmodernity
- Reconstruction of identity and African historical consciousness
- Afrocentrism vs Eurocentric Africanism
- The abyssal debt and cultural restitutions
- The symbolic and spiritual dimension in Afrodiasporas
- Repositioning Afrodescendant languages and cultures within a continuum of belonging and identification
- Pan-Africanism and the return to ancestral roots
- Integration of returnees into contemporary African societies
- Analysis of the economic and logistical obstacles to the return of African diasporas and ways of overcoming them
- Reflection on projective and pragmatic approaches to the return of African diasporic subjects and their implications for the future of Africa and its diaspora.
- These themes and many others can be addressed in the proposals for contributions, which can be included at the intersection of the following fields: Literary, artistic and philosophical sciences
- Sociology, ethnology, anthropology
- History, geography, demography
- Economics and political science
- Etc.

Submission guidelines

Abstracts of contributions (in French or English) of no more than 300 words, together with biobibliographical notes on the contributors, must be sent to the following address: nakanJEcontributions@gmail.com by 15 November 2024. The Scientific Committee will notify the authors of its decision by 30 November 2024. The international study day will be held online on 12 December 2024. Papers may be presented in English or French. The connection link will be specified at a later date. For any further information, please send an email to nakanjournal@gmail.com.